

EXPLORING LANGUAGE DEPENDENCY IN ULTRASOUND-TO-SPEECH SYNTHESIS

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In this work, we try to address the question of how transferable a UTS (ultrasound-to-speech) system is for the same speaker in a different linguistic context.

In this paper, we present a newly collected bilingual UTI dataset from three speakers producing audible speech in Azerbaijani (L1) and English (L2) in the same session.

The purpose of data collection was to prevent speaker and session dependency of UTI and solely focus on the effects of linguistic structure differences.

To observe the effects of linguistic differences, we try to explore language dependency of UTS system.

0. MOTIVATION

	speaker "01 az"	speaker "02 az"	speaker "03 az"
L1			
	train set: 40 rec dev set: 5 rec test set: 10 rec	train set: 38 rec dev set: 5 rec test set: 10 rec	train set: 40 rec dev set: 5 rec test set: 10 rec
L2			
	test set: 10 rec	test set: 10 rec	test set: 10 rec

1. DATA COLLECTION

	↓ MSE	
	L1 (az)	L2 (en)
01az	0.58	0.77
02az	0.61	0.87
03az	0.81	0.85

	↓ MCD	
	L1 (az)	L2 (en)
01az	3.91	3.94
02az	3.05	2.88
03az	3.77	3.79

vocoder MCD with original recordings

	↓ MCD	
	L1 (az)	L2 (en)
01az	1.55	1.69
02az	1.37	1.41
03az	1.46	1.51

3. EVALUATION

data pre-processing

Ultrasound scanline (64 × 842 px) → Bicubic interpolation → Resized to 64 × 128 px → Pixel normalization [-1, 1] → READY TO GO!

Original audio signal

Generated audio signal

Neural Vocoder - Speech Synthesis

For fair comparison utilized vocoder: HiFi-GAN | VCTK - V1

2. METHODOLOGY

MAIN TAKEAWAY:

LINGUISTIC CONTEXT SHOULD BE TAKEN INTO ACCOUNT WHILE CREATING UTS SYSTEMS.

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